

Automated differentiation of White Blood Cells images

Abstract: Automated medical image analysis offer a powerful tool for medical diagnosis such as the Differential Blood Count of the White Blood Cells (WBCs). The major requirement for this project is to have an efficient technique for segmenting a WBC into its Nucleus and Cytoplasm, feature extraction and classification. The segmentation process is performed by two main steps: Segmenting the WBC from the background (Red Blood Corpuscles (RBC), platelets and plasma) which is based on the difference between the Blue and Green components of the colored WBC image. In the second step; segmentation is for the WBC, into its Nucleus and Cytoplasm which is based on the histogram of the Green-component of the cell. A decision-tree based white blood cell (WBC) classification scheme for peripheral blood images is developed. Based on the sufficient analysis on the characteristics of white blood cells, 10 efficient features are extracted, including size, shape, intensity and color, and a classification scheme based on decision-tree is designed to classify 5 different types of normal white blood cells. The presented scheme is tested on 400 WBCs which are obtained under different dying and imaging conditions. Results show classification accuracy above 94%.

Keywords: *WBC, Image Segmentation, Differential Blood Count.*

1. Introduction

Human blood contains three major classes of cells: Leukocytes (WBCs), Erythrocytes (Red Blood Cells (RBCs)) and Thrombocytes (Platelets). All of these are produced in the bone marrow through successive proliferation and differentiation of hematopoietic stem cells. It is well known that Erythrocytes and Thrombocytes are ended as a single cell class. On the other hand, Leukocytes are grouped by their morphological appearance into five well known basic subclasses named Neutrophils (N), Eosinophils (E), Basophils (B), Monocytes (M), and Lymphocytes (L). The approximate normal distribution of the WBCs subclasses is known to be (50-70%N, 20-45%L, 2-10%M, 1-5%E and 0-1%B). Bacterial infections or leukemia as an example can cause deviations from this normal subclass distribution. The estimation of this distribution using the Differential Blood Count (DBC) is an important diagnostic tool. The traditional count involves manual microscopic examination of 100- 500 (typically 200) Leukocytes on a stained blood smear glass slide.

Automatic counting based on digital image analysis has been proposed by many authors [5,7,13,14,15,16,17,19]. Such systems collect images from standard blood smear slides through a microscope and a digital camera. Good segmentation algorithm is required in order to locate each cell. The accuracy of the subsequent classification depends on the correct segmentation process of the cells into its Nucleus and Cytoplasm [1,2,3,4,6,7,8,20]. Several researchers have previously proposed features to differentiate leukocyte (white blood cells) cells. Ongun [11] have worked on color smear images, containing both peripheral and immature cells. WBC's are segmented by morphological preprocessing combined with fuzzy patch labeling.

The Process involving segmentation, feature extraction and classification was proposed by *Sinha* [14] at which WBC segmentation is a two-step process carried out on the HSV-equivalent of the image, using K-Means clustering followed by EM-algorithm. Features

extracted from the segmented cytoplasm and nucleus. *Sabino [13,15]* used the pattern recognition methods for computer-aided diagnosis, considering a variety of morphometric features, expressing size and shape, color and texture. *Vincenzo [18]* proposed a system firstly individuates the leucocytes from the others blood cells in the blood image, then it extracts morphological indexes and finally it classifies the leucocytes by a neural classifier. The segmentation of leukocytes blood cells done based on histogram analysis [12] and measurement of distance among nuclei. *Rezatofigh [10]* have proposed the segmentation of white blood cell nucleus based on Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process for amplifying the desired colour vectors. A variety of semi-automatic or automatic methods have been proposed to segment cell boundaries. These methods include thresholding, watershed, nearest neighbourhood graphs, mean shift procedure and deformable models. The automatic classification of bacteria cells in digital microscopic images using simple shape geometric features is studied by *Hiremath [9]*.

In this paper, we have proposed an automated segmentation, feature extraction and classification of Leukocytes: Lymphocyte, Monocyte, Eosinophil Basophile, and Neutrophil in light microscopic images based difference of color components and threshold. The experimental results are compared with the manual results obtained by pathologist. The proposed method is more reliable and computationally less expensive.

2. Experimental method

Blood smears are stained with Leishman stain and the images are acquired using a Panasonic WV-CP220 series digital video camera, with an ATW (Automatic Tracing White balance) and a built in AGC (Automatic Gain Control). Minimum illumination of 0.5 lx at F0.75 and signal-to-noise ratio of 46dB by employing a 1/3 inch interline transfer CCD image sensor with 512(H) x 582 (V) pixels. The output signal is feed to a TV tuner in a Pentium-II 450 MHz Personal Computer, resulting 24-bit color image of 332(H) x 252(V) pixels, which is considered a suitable resolution to capture the cell and its nuclear material.

The camera is attached to light transmission microscope with 40x objective magnification which is directly connected to the microscope with no eye pieces. Slides are illuminated by 50 watt halogen lamp and focused by microscopic focusing system as shown in Figure (1).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Segmentation technique

Segmentation as a part of the data reduction stage involves the partitioning of the image plane into meaningful parts. The performance of any segmentation technique is limited by one or more of the following factors: significant case-specific distinctions in blood smear preparation, smear staining and image acquisition conditions. Most earlier proposed techniques are sensitive to the right selection of parameters such as, threshold, mask-size, initial contour, and the assumption of circular shape, which is untenable most of the times. Hence, a robust technique is devised, free from the above assumption, as well as, from the need of user intervention to tune the smear parameters.

In the present work a segmentation scheme Figure (2) is proposed to distinguish between the WBC Cytoplasm and Nucleus from the input smear image.

Figure (1) System Setup

Figure (2) Segmentation Scheme

The full description of the above segmentation scheme is given as follows:

At the first step, the captured smear image file is split up into its three color component bands Red, Green and Blue as shown in Figure (3). This results three grayscale files for the captured image by the camera of bitmap (bmp) format.

The three grayscale components are examined by Histogram analysis, for about 50 images covering all the five basic WBC types. It was found that the Green component is the better discriminator between WBCs and the rest of the smear's image. On the other hand, the Blue component lacks the appearance of the WBC (Cytoplasm and Nucleus), while the rest of the smear image background clearly appear.

Figure (3) Color Components of a WBC

At the second step, the difference between the Blue and Green component bands leads to the partial disappearance of the background. As a result of this second step, WBC is relatively distinguished from the back ground as shown in Figure (4).

At the third step, the *graythreshold*, a built-in function in Matlab software, is applied on the B-G smear image as proposed by *Gonzalez [5]* The result observed in Figure (5), is the binary form of the B-G smear image due to the computed threshold value from the above function.

Figure (4) Blue - Green Difference

Figure (5) Binary Blue – Green Image

At the fourth step, removal of the background (edges of the RBCs), appears in the thresholded image, is performed by applying an image erosion technique. This leads to the removal of the small objects and moreover, disconnects the large incompact objects into small ones as shown in Figure (6).

Sometimes, during the image capturing some of WBC's is touching the border of the image, so that those cells have to be removed from the image. The *imageclearborder* Matlab built-in function is applied to remove those objects touching the border of the image as shown in Figure (7). After those steps of erosion and clearing borders, some of small background objects may remain in the image.

Figure (6) Eroded Binary Image

Figure (7) Cell Image after Clearing Borders

In the sixth step, the object of maximum area is selected (in case of more than one object remained) which correspond to the eroded cell mask. A dilation process is applied, by the same structural element in erosion step, to recover the original area of the WBC mask before erosion as given in Figure (8).

At the seventh step, smoothing the WBC is performed by removing any small objects touching it. This is made by using a moving average window of suitable weight. Consequently, the *graythreshold* Matlab built-in function is applied to get the smoothed WBC mask as shown in Figure (9).

Figure (8) Cell Mask

Figure (9) Smoothed Cell Mask

At the last step, the cell mask is applied on the three original smear components and then making the corresponding histogram for each one. It is found that, the green masked component, shown in Figure (10) and its histogram in Figure (11) give the best discrimination between histogram peaks that can correspond to the cell's Nucleus and Cytoplasm.

Figure (10) Green Masked Component

Figure (11) Histogram of Green Masked Component

In order to find the threshold value, which correspond to of the minimum between the two main histogram peaks, a polynomial fitting process is performed. The computed threshold value is then automatically used to segment the Nucleus and Cytoplasm. The pixels values below the threshold is corresponding to the Nucleus as shown in Figure (12.a), while those above the threshold corresponding to the Cytoplasm as shown Figure (12.b).

Figure (12.a) Cell Nucleus Mask

Figure (12.b) Cell Cytoplasm Mask

The result of applying the present segmentation technique on a sample of 1000 images is tabulated in the following table:

Cell Type	No. of processed Images	No. of Correctly Segmented Images
Eosinophils (E)	18	16
Basophiles (B)	32	32
Lymphocyte (L)	309	297
Monocytes (M)	71	62
Netrophils (N)	570	556
Total Number	1000	963

Table 1: Results of the Segmentation Technique

From the above table, the percentage of correctly segmented cells has the value 96.3 % which is satisfactory in compassion with manual segmentation methods. An examples of segmentation results shown in figure (13).

Figure (13): Examples of Cell segmentation into Cytoplasm and Nucleus

3.2 Features extraction:

The feature selection is based on manual inspection of the results to select that feature which is suitable for certain subclass of cells rather than the others.

In this respect, the following ten features are selected for the 600 segmented cell images:

1. The difference between the average cytoplasm red component and the average cytoplasm green component; f1.
2. Number of nucleus's lobes; f2.

This parameter is automatically achieved with *Iterative Erosion Filtering (IEF)* technique of the nucleus mask. *vincenzo [18]*, following this technique, the number of lobes in a nucleus is corresponding to the maximum number of connected objects (lobes) during the iterative erosion procedure.

3. The difference between the average cytoplasm red component and the average nucleus red component; f3.
4. Compactness; f4.

Area and perimeter are parameters that describe the size of an object in one way or another. In order to compare objects that are observed from different distances, it is important to use shape parameters that do not depend on the size of the object at the image plane. The Compactness (C) is the simplest one, defined as $C = 4\pi A_{NU} / P_{NU}^2$ Where A and P are Nucleus area, nucleus perimeter respectively. The Compactness is a dimensionless with a maximum value of 1 for circles. Smaller values are generated from non compact shapes

5. The ratio between the nucleus areas to nucleus perimeter f5.
6. Soft Erosion: In this process erosion is made until the nucleus area becomes 50% of its original area. Accordingly, M nucleus remains as a single entity, while E nucleus is divided into two separate entities; f6.
7. The number of nucleus pixels (nucleus area); f7.
8. The number of cell (nucleus and cytoplasm) pixels (cell area); f8.
9. The ratio between the nucleus areas to cell area; f9.

10. The difference between the average Cytoplasm blue component and the average Nucleus blue component; f10.

Computed results for the above selected features are compiled in table 2 for the five WBC types.

Cell type	Neutrophils			Lymphocyte			Monocyte			Basophils			Eosinophils		
	Average	SD		Average	SD		Average	SD		Average	SD		Average	SD	
f1	28.70	2.19		14.68	3.52		23.32	2.45		0	0		42.01	3.311	
f2	2.959	0.40		1.109	0.26		2.037	0.09		2.875	0.664		2.285	0.234	
f3	63.11	5.65		25.69	22.9		31.70	2.46		-193	12.15		32.53	1.909	
f4	0.687	0.04		1.005	0.02		0.836	0.03		0.837	0.022		0.731	0.027	
f5	4.774	0.70		7.785	1.00		7.773	0.84		8.991	0.47		5.090	0.375	
f6	1.442	0.24		1.024	0.07		1.166	0.18		1.166	0.190		2	0	
f7	636.3	202.		813.1	283		1126	314.		1450.	106.3		606.9	46.8	
f8	1788.	656.		1321.	470		2445	940.		1464.	105.9		1687.	170.8	
f9	0.372	0.03		0.630	0.05		0.496	0.05		0.990	0.002		0.367	0.031	
F10	13.46	5.75		-11.49	24.8		-1.195	2.95		-245.2	6.802		-18.32	4.954	

Table 2: Average and stander deviation for selected features

3.3 CLASSIFICATION PROCESS:

The analysis of the previously given results (table, 1) is clearly indicates that only the following six features are selected for fairly classifying the five WBCs types. Those selected features, are given with their limiting values in table: 4.3. The following are the steps made for classifying the five WBC types which are detailed described in the classification scheme shown in figure: 4.

1. Cell of type B is classified using feature f1. As this cell type has no cytoplasm, so feature f1=0.
2. Cell of type L is classified using features f3 and f4. As this cell type has a single lobe, so feature f2=1, and for fair judgment feature f4 has to be greater than 0.95, otherwise the cell is considered undefined.
3. Cell of type N is classified using feature f3 to be greater than a limiting value (v_1). This limiting value is proposed for fair separation of cell type N (largest value N_1) and cell of type E (nearest value E_1) and their corresponding $3*SD$ value, N_{3SD} and E_{3SD} respectively. This value is computed automatically from the above mentioned values of f3 as follows

$$v_1 = [(N_1 - N_{3SD}) + (E_1 + E_{3SD})]/2$$

$$= [(63.117-16.97) + (32.532 + 5.7294)]/2= 42$$

4. Remaining cell types M and E are classified based on feature f5. Within the 3*SD error value there could be an over lapping between the value of f5 for two cell types under test, where:

(f5 ± 3*SD) is in the range {3.9641, 10.3206} for E type and in the range {5.226, 10.3206} for M type. Accordingly, cells of f5 ≤ 5.226 are classified as E cell type and of f5 ≥ 6.2161 are classified as M type. On the other hand cells in the overlapping range (5.226<f5< 6.216) are treated by an extra feature f6 called soft erosion, when f6=1 means cell is of type E and f6=2 means is of type M.

Those criteria are arranged in table 3.

Measure	Netrophils	Lymphocyte	Monocytes	Basophils	Eosinophils
f1	Not Zero	Not Zero	Not Zero	Zero	Not Zero
f2	>= 2	1	2	1	2 or 3
f3	63.008	22.44	31.302	-192	32.511
f4	<0.95	>0.95	<0.95	<0.95	<0.95
f5	-	-	>5.2	-	<6.2
f6	-	-	2	-	1

Table 3: Summary of selected features

From the above analysis the classification process can be sketched in the following classification scheme (fig 14).

Figure 14: Classification Scheme

3.4 TESTING

The confusion matrix is a common method of comparison of the performance of the classifier on data set. The confusion matrix is basically a matrix of the actual classes of data, shown against the class assigned by the classifier under investigation (table 4).

In this table 400 images were tested from the used 1000 one.

Class	N	L	M	B	E	Undefined
N (231)	220	0	2	0	3	6
L (123)	7	106	2	6	0	2
M (26)	0	0	24	0	1	1
B (12)	0	0	0	12	0	0
E (7)	0	0	0	0	7	0

Table 4: Conclusion Matrix

The last confusion matrix provides a great deal of information about which classes are likely to be confused. From table 4.4, the following conclusions can be extracted (based on the classifier and data set from which this matrix is drawn):

1. Class N have a probability of 220/231 (95.23%) of actually being of class N.
2. Class L have a probability of 106/123 (86.17%) of actually being of class L.
3. Class M have a probability of 24/26 (92.3%) of actually being of class M.
4. Class B is always classified correctly.
5. Class E is always classified correctly.

From above the average percentage of the correctly identified WBC has the value of 94.74 % which could be satisfactory in comparison with the other image based automated differential blood count techniques.

It is clear from the obtained results that this method is accurate and fast automation of differential white blood cells count, without human interaction (manual method) which leads to a high percentage error, due to the large effort and time lost in this process.

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References

- [1] Aus H.M., H.Harms, V. ter Meulen and U. Gunzer. (1987) “*Statistical Evaluation of Computer Extracted Blood Cell Features for Screening Populations to Detect Leukemias*”, Pattern Recognition Theory and Applications, Edited by P.A. Devjver and J. Kittler, Springer-Verlag Berlin, Heidelberg. pp. 132-1137.
- [2] Bins M., (1985) “Morphometry of white blood cells”, Pure & Appl. Chem., Vol. 57, No. 4, pp. 599-601.
- [3] Bikhet S. F. and A. M. Darwish and H. A. Tolba and S. I. Shaheen. (1999) “Segmentation and Classification of White Blood Cells”, *IEEE Intl. Conf. On Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, ICASSP*, pp. 2259-2261.
- [4] Canny, J., (1986) “A Computational Approach to Edge Detection”, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, Vol. PAMI-8. (6):679-698.
- [5] Gonzalez R.C., R.E Woods, S.L. Eddins. , (2004) “Digital image Processing Using Matlab”, Pearson Prentice Hall Person Education, Inc., New Jersey, USA.
- [6] Hindawi S. K., A. M. Abo-Zaid , I. H. Ibrahim, S. A. Mousa (2007) “Automated Segmentation of White Blood Cell Images”, Egyptian J. Biophysics, Vol. 13, No. 1 (2007) [In press]
- [7] Katz ARJ. (2000) “Image analysis and supervised learning in the automated differentiation of White Blood Cells from Microscopic images”, Minor Thesis. Melbourne: RMIT.
- [8] Kan Jiang¹ , Qing-Min Liao¹ and Yuan Xiong¹ (2005) “A novel white blood cell segmentation scheme based on feature space clustering”. *Soft Computing A Fusion of Foundations, Methodologies and Applications*. pp. 322-326.
- [9] P.S. Hiremath and Parashuram Bannigidad , Automatic Classification of Bacterial Cells in Digital Microscopic Images, ICDIP 2010, February 26-28, 2010 Singapore.

- [10] S. H. Rezatofghi, H. Soltanian-Zadeh, R. Sharifian and R. A. Zoroofi, "A New Approach to White Blood Cell Nucleus Segmentation Based on Gram-Schmidt Orthogonalization" IEEE International Conference on Digital Image Processing, pp. 107-111, 2009.
- [11] Ongun Guclu and Ugur Halici and Kemal Leblebicioglu and Volkan Atalay, (2001) "Feature Extraction and Classification of Blood Cells for an Automated Differential Blood Count System," *IEEE IJCNN*, pp. 2461-2466
- [12] Mohammad Hamghalam and Ahmad Ayatollahi, "Automatic Counting of Leukocytes in Giemsa-Stained Images of Peripheral Blood smear" IEEE International Conference on Digital Image Processing, pp. 13-16, 2009.
- [13] Sabino DMU, Costa L da F, Rizzati EG, Zago MA., (2004) "Toward leukocytes recognition using morphometry texture, and color". IEEE international symposium on biomedical imaging. volume 12 number pp. 1-6.
- [14] Sinha Neelam and A. G. Ramakrishnan., (2003) "Automation of Differential Blood count" IEEE.0-7803-7651-x/03/\$17.00.
- [15] Sabino D M U, Costa L F, Calado R T, Zago M A., (2003) "Automatic leukemia diagnosis". *ACTA Microscopica* 12(1):1-6.
- [16] Song X and Abu-mostafa Y and Sill J and Kasdan H. (1997) "Incorporating contextual information in white blood cell image identification". *Neural Information Processing Systems*. vol., 10 of *NIPS* , MIT Press.
- [17] Vassili A.Kovalev and Andrei Y.Grigoriev and Hyo-Sok Ahn. 1996 "Robust Recognition of White Blood Cell Images". *Int. Conf on Pattern Recognition* pp. 371-375.
- [18] Vincenzo Piuri and fabio Scotti. (2004) "Morphological Classification of Blood Leucocytes by Microscopic Images". IEEE international Conference on Computational Intelligence for Measurements System and Applications Boston, MD, USA, 14-16 July.
- [19] Khashman Adnan, (2008) "IBCIS: Intelligent blood cell identification system" *Progress in Natural Science* 18, 1309–1314
- [20] YazanM. Alomari, et. Al, (2014) "Automatic Detection and Quantification of WBCs and RBCs Using Iterative Structured Circle Detection Algorithm" *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine* Volume 2014, Article ID 979302, 17 page